

Mani Man Singh Rajbhandari and Mohini Shakya*
St. Xavier's College, Maitighar, Kathmandu, Nepal
*Email: manirajbhandari@sx.edu.np**

Managing Organizational Crisis for performance, production, productivity and profitability

Abstract: Managing organizational crisis requires both leadership and management. While organizational performances, production, productivity and profitability are concerned, both managerial techniques and organizational leadership are desired to effectively manage and interconnect the organizational available resources for the decision making process. Managing a crisis requires attention from leaders and managers for resolving the immediate issue arising from the internal and external organizational environment. In doing so, Factor of Organizational Productivity (FOP) which includes a Leader, Followers and Context need to be incorporated with the existing available resources to manage the crisis. The quantitative methodology was applied to conduct this study. A questionnaire was developed and pilot-tested before collecting data from the participants. Small entrepreneurial industries were selected for this study. Data were collected from 100 participants. The data were further processed for analysis through SPSS analytical software to find the correlation between various variables that were attached to the concept of this study. The findings suggest that organizational performances, production, productivity and profitability are not significantly correlated within the organizational setting and between the functional departments which showed $r = -0.469$ analyzed, shown from the organizational training and development activities. The results suggest that leadership autocratic style is stronger in the organization within the followers (employees) focused parameters. The findings also suggest that leader's productivity is negatively correlated $r = -0.043$. It was found that production and performances are interconnected. The results analyses show that effective time management and employees managing their time are negatively correlated. However, managing people's ability of the organizational leader is positive $r = 0.171$. In addition, it was found that managing crisis ability with relation to crisis management is negatively correlated with $r = -0.213$.

Keywords: organization, leadership, management, time management, controlling, organizing, quantitative

Introduction

Organization entirely depends on its resources. These resources are comprises of various components, such as finance, raw materials, technologies, humans, etc. Among these various components, human resources can

be very important, while they are also very sensitive, emotional, natural and can have various values apart from organizational values and cultures. Rajbhandari et al., (2017) state that organizational culture can have various micro-climates, which generate its own clusters of sub cultures. These micro-climates can generate positive and negative environments within one organizational culture. Moreover, these micro-climates can have a significant impact on performances, productions, productivity and profitability. It is therefore necessary for entrepreneurs to manage these aspects of human resources for organizational performance, production, productivity and profitability. This is closely related to managing people or managing human crises within an organizational setting to achieve the organizational goal of performances, production, productivity and profitability.

Today's organizations have become complex, this further generates dynamic environments with multiple crises and further demands organizational leaders to acquire with additional competency to manages the crises, for which dynamic organizational leadership is required.

Rajbhandari (2021) states that dynamic leadership styles have become essential in today's business, especially in light of the COVID-19 post-pandemic circumstances. As a result of dynamic leadership and a dynamic environment, all Factors of Organizational Productivity (FOP) experience a dynamic movement. This Factor of Organizational Productivity (FOP) has three characteristics: followers, leaders, and organizational context (Rajbhandari, 2021). All of these Factors of Organizational Productivity (FOP) comprise the circle of organizational operational activities; any loss of momentum can cause the company to fall behind, necessitating significant effort to keep up with today's fast-paced dynamic environment.

It has become important for organizational leaders to manage internal crisis, consisting of people working for the organization, for achieving the organizational common goals. When employees are satisfied with the way their leader handles a crises, they are more productive. Employees have more faith in the future of the company. The performance of a company's personnel determines its production (Bah, 2015). In the end, an employee's capacity to do tasks successfully and efficiently, in order to advance the company's goals, determines the success of any firm (Bundy, 2017).

Studies on employee performance are related to a variety of factors. Organizations are better able to manage their production when they can comprehend the influence of their employees' performance (Saddam and Abu Mansor, 2015). An earlier study found that a key factor in determining organizational success is employee performance. However, businesses must employ efficient performance measurements in order to meet the goals. The worldwide environment is undergoing dramatic changes. The company will boost operating productivity during the transitions because the workers' trust in their capacity to meet organizational objectives will grow as a result of the skills they have acquired (Anitha, 2014). When a company's plan to resolve the crisis fails, workers may experience serious consequences as a result of crisis management (Pop, 2017). Additionally, the business must incur additional costs to keep personnel by increasing employee pay and making sure that everyone works together. Additionally, employees are unable to ensure that all operations run efficiently, which makes it challenging for them to understand the organization's aims and objectives.

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Naylor, Gkolia and Brundrett (2006) assert that a problem-free organization can only exist in a stable environment. The three pillars of any organizational structure are organization, leadership, and communication, and they establish the parameters for its operations (Naylor et al., 2006). Employee performance may be maximized at all levels and under all circumstances when a company is able to attract and develop its human resources and foster organizational cultures of commitment (Bouradas, 2005).

Effective crisis management begins with a shared understanding that a threat has arisen that necessitates immediate action. A random sample of investigation reports gives the impression that most disasters could have been predicted. That is not a fair (or reasonable) assessment. When the conclusion is obvious, it appears that a crisis was unavoidable (Turner, 1978; Tetlock, 2005; Woods, 2005). A crisis or tragedy frequently necessitates strong collaboration among a diverse range of groups, many of which have never worked together before (Hart, 2022). When a society faces a crisis, its citizens will look to its leaders for guidance on how to interpret the situation and what steps to take to restore normalcy.

According to Rajbhandari, (2021), leadership is more than just making changes; it is also about adjusting to those changes, creating environments for followers to adapt to those changes, and fostering a harmonious climate within current change settings. New and unplanned organizational behavioral settings emerge as a result of the dynamism of both internal and external environmental pressures. These pressures generate crisis; while internal environment crisis can be controlled, the external pressure could be difficult to control. This further creates agitations within an organizational internal culture.

Effective crisis management requires resilient organizations that can withstand blows and recover quickly. The problem is that we do not know how to build a strong resilient organization (Comfort, Boin and Demchak, 2010). One of the most important aspects of establishing well-prepared, resilient companies is to engage in continuous preparatory practices such as vulnerability analysis, drills, scenario exploration, and network exercises. This can be achieved through additional training and developmental activities, which leaders of an organization must integrate with all the functional departments. These activities foster a culture of alertness, a sense that things could go wrong, and a shared belief that everyone involved is ready to deal with whatever threat they face (Weick and Sutcliffe, 2007). As a result of hard work and participation, resilience can be considered as a result of resilience.

Shakya (2022) concludes that leadership is necessary to manage any kind of crisis within the organizational setting for achieving performance, production, productivity and profitability. Shakya (2022) also states that organizational demagogues are responsible for planning, organizing, leading and communicating along with managing human resources, policies, technologies, training to avoid the seemingly unmanageable crisis to achieve organizational performance, production, productivity and profitability.

Thus the purpose of this study is to explore the organizational leader's competence for achieving organizational performance, production, productivity and profitability through managing the complex and dynamic organizational internal environment. For this, the study seeks to explore through the following research questions.

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Research questions

1. How do organizational leaders manage crisis for achieving performance, production, productivity and profitability?
2. To what extent are performance, production, productivity and profitability being managed and organized in a crisis situation?

Research Methodology

This is a quantitative investigation. Primary data served as the primary source in this quantitative study, from which the quantitative examination was carried out using statistical tools. Participants in Bagmati-based organizations/industries in Kathmandu provided primary data for this study. The primary data was collected in an industrial district in Kathmandu Valley.

The sample size for this study was 100 employees. A questionnaire was created to conduct this research. The questionnaire was created at St. Xavier's College in Maitighar. The questionnaire was pilot-tested before going into the field to collect raw data. This assured the validity and reliability of the questionnaire. The relative movements of two or more sets of time series data are examined using cross-correlation analysis. It is used to objectively examine several time series to determine how well independent, moderate, pre-condition, and dependent variables match and, more importantly, when the best match occurs.

Among the 100 participants 57 were male and 43 were female, and the majority of the workers had only a primary level of education.

A correlation coefficient indicates how comparable the measurements of two or more variables are across a dataset. When the value is one, there is a perfect positive correlation; when the value is zero, there is no relationship between the variables; and when the value is between zero and one, there is a moderate relationship between the variables. Data analysis was done with the help of SPSS.

Results and analysis

A correlation coefficient indicates how comparable two or more variables' measurements are across a dataset. When the value is 1 there is perfect positive correlation, when the value is 0 there is no relationship between the variables and when the value is in between 0 and 1 then there is a moderate relationship between the variables.

Table 1 Correlation between managing crisis ability from managers with the crisis management

Correlations	Independent Variables	
Managing Crisis ability	Crisis management	
	Pearson Correlation	Sig. (2-tailed)
Performance	-0.213	0.033

Managing crisis with time	0.050	0.621
Effective time management	-0.021	0.835
Employees managing time	-0.118	0.244

The above Table 1 represents the correlation between managing ability during a crisis and management of crisis within an organizational environment. Correlation between these two variables is represented with $r = -0.213$, significance = 0.033, for managers' performance in running an organization during a crisis period. This represents the negative correlation coefficient between these two variables. However, managing crisis ability with time from the organizational leader is positive with the correlation 0.050 but is significantly moderate. Moreover, managing crisis ability with regard to time management and employees managing their time is negatively correlated with the ability to manage crisis from the manager's level. The correlation coefficient between managers' ability with effective time management and employees managing their time is $r = -0.021$ and -0.118 with significance differences of 0.835 and 0.244 respectively.

Table 2 Correlation between leaders ability with managing people

Correlations	Independent Variables	
	Managing people for crisis management	
Leadership ability	Pearson Correlation	Sig. (2-tailed)
The manager performance to run the organization	0.171	0.089
Organizing time for employees	-0.059	0.561
Effective time management	0.256	0.01
Employees managing time	-0.206	0.04

In Table 2, the correlation is represented between leaders ability with managing people for crisis management. The manager performance has represented skills in managing people; other variables related to organizing time and employees managing time shows that leaders are not able to demonstrate their skills to effectively manage the organizational internal affairs. This represents the negative production, productivity, and profitability of an organization. Although the performance of leader correlation is positive with managing people with $r = 0.171$ with a significance difference of 0.089, the performance of employees working under the leaders' supervision is not adequately managed. The result analysis of effective time management and employees managing their time is negative with the correlation of $r = -0.059$ (sig 0.561) and -0.206 (sig (0.04) respectively. This analysis represents the negative in production, productivity and profitability. However, the positive correlation between leaders ability to effective time management is $r = 0.256$ (sig 0.01).

The analysis also represents that timing supervision and leaders' ability to performance is positive but the internal time management of employees in a self-managing crisis is negative. Effective time management is considered as a pivotal aspect of organizational lives. It can therefore be interpreted that these indicators such as effectiveness, organizing, planning, communication, and leading have to be taken into consideration to

increase the employees' performance, production, productivity, and profitability simultaneously for the overall growth of an organization as a whole.

Table 3 Correlation between the introduction of a new policy and leaders' ability to management

Correlations	Independent Variables	
	Strategic policy introduced for management productivity and profitability	
SAKCIED	Pearson Correlation	Sig. (2-tailed)
The managerial techniques	-0.033	0.746
Organizing	-0.11	0.276
Effectiveness with time	0.081	0.422
Employees' management	0.364	0.001

In Table 3, correlation between strategic policy and managerial techniques is represented. The table represents the analysis of leaders' Skills, Ability, Knowledge, Competences, Intelligence and Experimental Determination (SAKCIED) (Rajbhandari, 2022). The results suggest that managerial techniques of applying SAKCIED are found negative in the performance of managerial techniques $r = -0.033$ (sig 0.746) and organizing the strategic policy with the negative correlation of $r = -0.11$ (sig 0.276). Whereas effectiveness with time is found to be positive with $r = 0.081$ (sig 0.422), human resources management is also found to be positive with $r = 0.364$ (sig 0.001).

The results suggest that managing crisis with leaders SAKCIED towards organizational productivity and profitability is found to be highly insignificant. This is due to the lack of knowledge about the contextual setting and strategic plans and policy implemented that relates with both internal and external environment.

Table 4 Correlation between the productivity and leaders' efficiency

Correlations	Independent Variables	
	The production efficiency	
Productivity	Pearson Correlation	Sig. (2-tailed)
Performance efficiency	-0.043	0.674
Organizing	0.277**	0.005
Time management	-0.099	0.328
Controlling	0.084	0.408

Production and performances are interconnected. However, a mismatch between performances and production generates inefficiency of organizational productivity. In Table 4, results suggest that leaders' performances are negatively correlated with the productivity of an organization with a correlation value of $r = -0.043$ (sig 0.674). This can be due to the time management of employees and the managers involved with the production line. Although organizing and controlling are found to be positively correlated with the

correlation value of $r = 0.277$ (sig 0.005) and 0.084 (sig 0.408), the organizational productivity cannot be considered significantly contributing to the organizational sustainability in the long run (Table 4).

Productivity highly relies on the performance efficiency of a leader. But the results suggest that leaders' performance is negatively correlated. This can be due to hesitation with regard to the introduction of strategic planning and policy to manage crisis. It can be assumed that organizing and controlling are found to be positive because of a strong controlling mechanism of leadership ability alone, which may have resulted in an autocratic leadership style display within the organizational internal environment. It is evident from the results that *leadership multi-flex styles blend* was not applied by the leader to fit within the followership domain and contextual settings (Rajbhandari, 2022).

Table 5 Correlation between delays in production leaders' performance

Correlations	Independent Variables	
	Delayed in Production Process	
Leaders performances	Pearson Correlation	Sig. (2-tailed)
Leaders' Ability	0.262**	0.008
Organizing	-0.255*	0.01
Time management	0.349**	0.001
Controlling	0.223*	0.026

In Table 5, the results suggest that the lack of leaders' ability towards managing crisis with increased production process is significantly correlated with the $r = 0.262$ (sig 0.008). This can be interpreted to mean that the lack of leaders' ability to increase production was not significantly contributing towards the productivity and profitability of an organization. A delay in the production process can cause significant loss to an organization's productivity and profitability in the long run. The results also suggest that organizing of management decisions with strategic plans and policy was not adequately furnished or efficiently managed. This further can generate an additional crisis to the organization.

However, the results also suggest that time management and controlling have a significant correlation of $r = 0.349$ (sig 0.001) and $r = 0.223$ (sig 0.026). This can be interpreted to mean that the leadership style is autocratic with strong emphasis on time management and a strong controlling mechanism. However, the controlling mechanism with time management and working hours does not alone determine the performances of employees.

Table 6 Correlation between the organization performance and leadership ability

Correlations	Independent Variables	
	The Organization Performance	
Leadership ability	Pearson Correlation	Sig. (2-tailed)
Managerial techniques	0.104	0.304
Organizing	-0.088	0.386

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Time management	0.246*	0.014
Controlling	0.334**	0.001

In Table 6, the results suggest that overall organizational performance is positive with application of managerial techniques within the different organizational functional departments. The correlation of application of managerial techniques is found to be positive with $r = 0.104$ (sig 0.304); however, the organizing techniques of leaders' ability is found to be negatively correlated with $r = -0.088$ (sig 0.386).

The results also suggest that leadership autocratic styles are stronger in the organization within the followers' (employees') focused parameters, which can be interpreted to mean that single leadership style is without a multi-flex blend which positively correlated with $r = 0.246$ (sig 0.014) for time management and $r = 0.334$ (sig 0.001) for controlling the employees timing for arriving on time for work and leaving from work. Nevertheless, for other aspects of organizational lives, in connection to performance, production, productivity and profitability, multi-flex leadership blend was activated as shown in Table 1 organizing time for employees for crisis management and in Table 4 for production efficiency.

Table 7 Correlation between the effectiveness of training and development

Correlations	Independent Variables	
	The effectiveness of training and development	
Performances	Pearson Correlation	Sig. (2-tailed)
Effectiveness	-0.469**	0.001
Organizing	-0.08	0.43
Time management	0.134	0.184
Controlling	0.162	0.107

From the Table 7, it can be interpreted that effectiveness of training and development is negatively correlated with $r = -0.469$ (sig 0.001). The results also suggest that time management and controlling have a positive correlation with effectiveness during the training sessions, which the results suggest in the correlation value of $r = 0.134$ (sig 0.184) for time management and $r = 0.162$ (sig 0.107) for controlling.

It is evident from the results and analysis that the organizational performances, production, productivity, and profitability are not significantly correlated within the organizational setting and between the functional departments. However, in Table 7, the results also suggest that organizing for the efficacy of training was found to be negatively correlated, which shows $r = -0.08$ (sig 0.43).

Discussion

Organizational performance, production, productivity, and profitability are expected to grow and be desired by all entrepreneurs. For this to be achieved, all functional departments of an organization need to be organized, planned, controlled and led in the goal-oriented direction. Moreover, to achieve the desired goal

of an organization, an equal level of commitment from both the entrepreneurs and the employees is required. However, the commitment level varies among the employees and between the departments. In such cases, to increase the commitment level of employees in an organization, a leader must seek for attitudinal commitment. Rajbhandari (2021) states that an organization of any kind must seek to achieve attitudinal commitment to nurture the Open Source Understanding (OSU). Open Source Understanding (OSU) is a mind-set attribute and can remain consistent.

However, Rajbhandari (2021) further states that most organizational actors perform their behavioural commitment, which is the Close Source Understanding (CSU) that is attached with the employees' personality and styles. For any organization to grow in their performance, production, productivity and profitability, a leader must develop the OSU and surpass the CSU, eventually creating a vibration within an organization and producing a Collision of Acceptance (COA). This state of mind-set can be generated through the implication of OSU. While the COA is necessary to generate, it further generates a stagnant context within an organizational context. However, if the consistency in the organizational context is not maintained, a Collision of Ignorance (COI) can surpass the COA; therefore the CSU will also surpass the OSU. Thus, it can be interpreted that for the growth of organization through the performance, production, productivity, and profitability, a leader must gain confidence among the employees from all functional departments with the OSU and COA.

For an organization to grow, productivity and profitability are of utmost importance in determining organizational development. For this proper planning and organizing are required. Moreover, managing crisis requires strategies that need to be properly planned and organized in connection to various organizational resources. Kerr (2006) states that small enterprises apply Quality Management System (QMS) informally on a basis level for organizational efficiency and market competitiveness. In this connection, the findings suggest from this study a negative correlation with other aspects of organizational lives, such as leaders' performances, organizing, and planning for crisis management. However, the findings suggest that there is a positive correlation between the leaders' planning, and organizing, and their controlling over the employees with monitoring for time and the management of time schedules of work for the employees while managing the crisis within an organizational internal environment.

Managing crisis is complex and difficult. McNulty and Marcus (2020) state that crisis brings about both complexity and change while it requires immediate attention by leading and managing the management process system with the proper allocation of resources. The findings suggest that the entrepreneurs in this study were managing but not leading their organization. This is supported by the results from Tables 4, 5, 6 and 7. The organization for managing crisis was not completely focusing on all the aspects of crisis within the functional departments, but was only stagnant with regard to production and performance which completely ignored productivity and profitability. It was also found that the managers were able to manage the present contextual settings but were not fully visionary. McNulty and Marcus (2020) further state that "the solution is to seek order rather than control". Moreover, the findings in this study suggest that organizational leaders were focused on controlling but not on order of the organizational resources and functional departments within an organizational internal management setting.

Conclusion

Performance, production, productivity, and profitability are important components and are closely connected for the assessment of organizational growth. These components are interconnected with all functional departments of an organization. Underperformances of any one of the organizational functional departments can affect the management system process leading to negative outcomes on performance, production, productivity, and profitability. For the organization to grow on a continuous pace, all departments must have their organizing and planning management systems, especially, during a managing crisis, leadership and management must coordinate to initiate the strategic management. Where planning and organizing are concerned, most organizations in Nepal are concerned with controlling and monitoring. When planning and organizing specifically for controlling and monitoring are initiated, this can lead to autocratic behavior of the leader. The autocratic tendencies may distort the actual strategic fit to achieve the organizations common goal towards performance, production, productivity, and profitability.

In this study, it was found that the leadership controlling mechanism was autocratic, focusing only on time management for the employees. However, the employees of the organization were incapable of managing their timing while at work. The results show that there is a negative correlation between time management and the employees' capacity to manage their time at work. This increased the deficiency in production, productivity and profitability. Moreover, managerial techniques with the leaders' SAKCIED were not positively correlated with the performances and productions which lead to a decrease in productivity and profitability. Managerial techniques were positively correlated with controlling the employees, which was possible with the leader's autocratic style.

References

- Anitha, J. (2014). Determinants of Employee Engagement and Their Impact on Employee Performance. *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, 63, 308-323.
- Bah, E. H. (2015). Impact of the business environment on output and productivity in Africa. *Journal of Development Economics*, 114, 159-171.
- Bouradas D. (2005). Leadership: a way to continuous success , Chapter5: People first, Kritiki publications. 50-53.
- Bundy, J. P. (2017). Crises and crisis management: Integration, interpretation, and research development. . *Journal of management*, 43(6), 1661-1692.
- Comfort, L.K., Boin, R.A. and Demchak,C. (2010) *Designing Resilience : Preparing for extreme events*. Pittsburgh, PA: Pittsburg University Press.
- Hart, T. P. (2022). Teaching crisis management before and after the pandemic: Personal Reflections. *Teaching Public Administration*, 0(0) 1–10.
DOI: 10.1177/01447394221087889
- Kerr, I R. (2006). Leadership Strategies for Sustainable SME Operation. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 15, 30–39. . DOI: 10.1002/bse.451

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- McNaulty, E. J. & Marcus, L. (2020). Are You Leading Through the Crisis ... or Managing the Response? Retrieved on 14th July, 2022 from https://hr.umich.edu/sites/default/files/are_you_leading_through_the_crisis_or_managing_the_response.pdf
- Naylor, P. Gkolia, M. & Brundrett, M. (2006). Leading from the Middle' an initial study of impact.
- Pop, Ş. (2017). Prevention and crisis management. *International Conference Knowledge-Based Organization*, 23(1). 246-250. doi:10.1515/kbo-2017-0039. 246-250.
- Rajbhandari, M. M. S. (2022). Dominant leadership styles: A multi-flex leadership styles blend towards the educational effectiveness. *Journal of educational thought*, 55(1), 69-88.
- Rajbhandari, M. M. S. (2021). Attitudinal and behavioural commitment of students whilst being supervised on their thesis writing. An experiential learning study at St. Xavier's College, maitighar, Kathmandu. *SXC Journal of management and social sciences*, 1(1), 1-18.
- Rajbhandari, M. M. S. (2021). Why Do We Need New Leadership Styles in Today's Organizations? *Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences*, 5(1), 64-71.
- Rajbhandari, M. M. S. Rajbhandari, S., Looock, C. & Du Plessis P. (2017). Enriching School Culture and Climate through Leadership in Collectivistic Educational Settings: Cases from Nepal and South Africa. *International Journal of Educational Sciences*, 18(1-3), 134-146. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/09751122.2017.1351076>
- Saddam, A. K. & Abu Mansoor N.N. (2015). The role of recruitment and selection practices in the organizational performance of Iraqi oil and gas sector: a brief literature review. *Review of European Studies*, 7(11), 348-358.
- Shakya, M. (2022). *Crisis management and the leader's ability to drive organization towards Productivity*. Masters Dissertation, St. Xavier's College, Maitighar. Retrieved from <https://ordt.com.np/students-publication/> on 13th, July, 2022. <https://ordt.com.np/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/CRISIS-MANAGEMENT-AND-THE-LEADERS-ABILITY-TO-DRIVE-ORGANIZATION-TOWARDS-PRODUCTIVITY.pdf>
- Tetlock, P. (2005). *Expert Political Judgment: How Good is It? How Can We Know?* Princeton, N.J.: Princeton University Press.
- Turner, B. A. (1978). *Man-made Disasters*. London: Wykeham.
- Weick, K. E. & Sutcliffe, K.M. (2007). *Managing the Unexpected Resilient Performance in an Age of Uncertainty*.
- Woods, D. D. (2005). Creating Foresight: Lessons for Enhancing Resilience from Columbia. In *Organization at the Limit: Lessons from the Columbia Disaster*, edited by William H. Starbuck and Moshe Farjoun. Oxford: Blackwell Publishing . 289-308.

